

Impact of Stress and Emotional Reactions due to the Covid-19 Pandemic in India

K. C. Meenakshi
(Lecturer)

Institute of hotel Management and catering technology

Abstract:- Covid-19 has resulted in disruption to many lives. Here we provide a brief report on 80 respondents' perception and emotional well-being due to covid-19. In late June 2021, Participants responded to the uncertainty regarding mental health as well as a significant level of stress and difficulty coping with covid-19 disruption. These outcomes were related to the higher level of emotional reactions and external locus of control. Male participants reported worst emotional and stressed well-being than compared female participants. This result suggests that some participants may be at particular risk for stress and poor emotional well being due to pandemic and highlight the urgent need for intervention and prevention strategies.

Keywords:- Literature, Stress, Emotional Reactions, Pandemic, Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

The corona virus disease, 2019 (COVID-19) began in the city of Wuhan in China and has quickly spread around the world, by generating the global health crisis with massive disruption/ proportions. Due to which people found themselves and forced to cope with new emotional reaction challenges mainly with stress, inducing a considerable degree of fear and worry with underlying health conditions. This pandemic has caused a real threat both physically and emotionally. According to research the people's life has been severely restricted, slow down due to the spread of the virus with adverse psychosocial consequences. The covid-19 is not just a medical phenomenon that simultaneously affecting each individual which is marked with the effect of level of severity, pain, and causing disruption.

According to global scenarios the recent study revealed that this pandemic exerts the people with fear that their close ones or they might become ill or may die by generating psychological stress and emotional breakdown. The impact of the pandemic is drastically changing the lives of many people, including the lives of young people. As schools and universities have closed exams and are postponed, the usual health information service is limited, socializing with friends and wider family is discouraged. In these circumstances can be tough for people as it affects social, physical and mental wellbeing. Research says there are 74% of Indians suffering from stress; 88% reported anxiety amid Covid-19. 68.6% of therapists reported the increase in the number of people they see and, in the hours, they spend taking therapy.

According to a study conducted by a Delhi-based mental health service platform The Center of Healing (TCOH), there has been an increase in stress and anxiety among people since the Covid-19 pandemic. The study revealed that the rates of relapse among people who had recovered from mental health conditions have risen and due to the spike in need for their services. It noted that ever since the pandemic hit India over few months back, followed by an unprecedented lockdown, stress and anxiety levels have been on the rise. Stress poses many challenges compared to society as it hinders people's life from acquiring poor emotional reactions which are significantly associated with elevated levels of stress.

II. OBJECTIVE

- To study the relationship between the level of stress and emotional reactions. This study sought to accomplish the following research objectives.
- To determine the level of stress experienced by the Indians.
- To determine the level of emotional reactions by Indians.
- To identify if there is any significant relationship between the level of stress and emotional reactions by Indians.

III. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section provides the related literature which provides the strong foundation and scientific basis of this research. A total of 78% of Indian people experience various degrees of stress. The stressors can be categorized under social, cultural and environmental factors. As per the reports 74% of Indians experience stress and emotional reactions during this pandemic and simultaneously 88% reported anxiety amid COVID-19. Students report experiencing academic stress as the large amount of content to be mastered in a small amount of time (Abouserie, 2020). Reportedly the patients, medical staff, older adults and children are vulnerably experiencing to stress and emotional reactions, mainly psychological health issues during COVID-19 pandemic (Erkutulu &Chafra, 2020). In addition to that COVID-19 pandemic affects and creates the correlated stress and emotional reactions among the citizens of India. Most of the researchers hold the certain percentage of Indian people who finds it difficult to survive this COVID-19 due to negative thoughts and environment (Baker, 2021). The hustling and buzzing works given by schools, colleges and universities during this pandemic can also create various stress and emotional reactions among students, staff and many more. During this COVID-19 pandemic the environment has been challenging such as course overload, limited work opportunities, financial crisis and many more of

all of which creates the source of stress and emotional reactions such as fear, tension and anxiety in many Indian people (Sinha, Sharma and Nepal 2001). Relationship with family, friends and significant others can also be stressful (Elizabeth Scott, 2010).

Investigators have examined a wide variety of daily life stressors. The interpretation of some of these studies shows that it is difficult because they include the factors such as stress which shows its negative impact on emotional reactions of most of the individuals and extent of the perceived threat. Kornberg and Alison (2018) noted that the stress and emotional reactions are interdependent on each other. As it mainly depends on the face of a changing environment. Stress can affect anything which causes a change in the homeostasis of an individual. Folk man and Cannon (2019) said most of the reality situations depend on the individual's emotional reactions towards the intensity of their behavior and might show the controllability of stressor. To some situations it also features the cognitive responses according to individual's appraisals. Life events such as anger, anxiety, fear and many such things are major dependent/ associated with person's behavior. Garmezy and Johnson (2019) stated in contrast to stress and emotional reactions during any negative situation and over thinking about this situation can lead to the disease and might decrease one's confidence level. Because stress

and emotional reactions are too strong and they are too persistent in individuals which is biologically vulnerable to the age, and constitutional factors if they have poor coping skills.

The group or the research unit in this article had shown most of the stress and emotional reactions statements. As the impact of stress, emotional reactions might be different among the individuals. The qualitative study of the work stress and emotional reactions has been implemented among the individuals due to carelessness of not following rules and regulations. The continuous presence of these variables might alter the body and aspects of nervous system. But it is obvious that most of the individuals are unaware of the importance and effectiveness of coping techniques during this COVID-19 due to stress and emotional reactions. There was the longitudinal study where the stress and emotional reactions level were measured and have been provided with proper treatment and guidance or any other coping strategies in order to reduce stress and emotional reactions among the individuals.

This figure shows the independent and dependent variable of the study. The independent variable is the stress and the dependent variable is the emotional reactions among Indians.

Fig. 1: The schematic diagram of the level of stress in relation to the emotional reactions due to COVID-19 among Indians

IV. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the stress and emotional reactions among Indians. These include different aged groups of Indian people, ages 18 years and above. Researcher's limit their study all over India specifically in universities where the survey will be conducted at the respondents own respected room using the like type of questionnaire.

Researchers understand the level of stress and emotional reactions among different Indians. Therefore the study focuses on the 60 respondents from different universities. The limitation of this study is the type of sampling being used which is probability sampling technique.

The researcher also includes ethical consideration such as giving informed consent before conducting the survey. Due to the sensitivity of the topic, names of the respondents were not included and information that has been gathered will not be divulged to others without permission.

V. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will benefit the following:

- **Respondents:** This study aims to give relevant information about the stress and emotional reactions in India. This will benefit the participants, people as well as students in India. Since they are the ones who experience stress and emotional reactions due to the covid-19 pandemic. And to be aware of the stress and its impact on the emotional reactions.
- **Educational Institutions:** this study aims to give relevant information about the stress and emotional reactions concerning educational institutions. By giving relevant information about the individual's behavior how he/she behave or react, which shows the impact on physically and mentally.
- **Family and friends:** This study promotes the knowledge to the family as well as the friends about the stress and emotional reactions experienced by their loved ones and helps them to understand better.
- **Teachers:** This study helps to understand their students about the problems faced by them and be aware to know the level of stress and emotional reactions.
- **Future researchers:** This research may encourage further investigation and serve as data to make future researchers significant in measuring the level of stress and emotional reactions.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the study’s research design, research locale, population and sample, research instrument, data collection, ethical considerations and statistical tool.

VII. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study will use a quantitative research method specifically, the descriptive correlation method wherein findings were expressed numerically. The descriptive correlation will be used to determine if there is a correlation

between stress and emotional reactions among the respondents. This method is used to correlate with two or more number of variables to see if it exists, rather it cannot cause and affect the relationships.

This study will be conducted through an online survey such as Google Forms. This study is conducted to measure the impact of stress and emotional reactions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is mainly grouped under the province by the India statistic authority.

VIII. POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The respondents of this study will be 80 respondents from all over India, age 18 years and above. A stratified sampling technique is used to determine the respondents. The probability sampling technique involves the division of a population into smaller groups or strata. In this study, there is a population of 150 from which randomly 80 respondents will be picked up through probability sampling technique

IX. RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The researchers will use an instrument adapted from the Academic Stress scale (1.00- 3.50). This scale consists of 10 items describing the stress among the respondent’s life due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The level of stress they feel for

each item can be indicated by marking a checkmark in the bracket given against each statement. The objective of this scale is to measure the stress among the respondents during this pandemic (COVID-19). It contains 10 items and each item had a scale to determine if the respondent strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree with the statements.

The researchers also used a modified scale to measure the level of emotional reactions (1.00-3.50) among the respondents. The scale is composed of 8 statements and each item has a scale to determine if the respondent strongly disagrees, strongly agrees, disagree, or agrees to the statements. The answers of the respondents according to what he/she believes in were rated by using the Likert scale.

Scale	Range of mean scores	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very high level of stress/very low level of emotional reactions
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	High level of stress/ low level of emotional reactions
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Low level of stress/ high level of emotional reactions
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very low level of stress/ very high level of emotional reactions

X. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

In the course of the research, the researcher will be taking the specific measure. The conduct will be observed by the ethical guidelines.

- **Rights and dignity of participants:** The researchers will be respecting the right, safeguarding the dignity and protecting the welfare of research participants through cultural sensitivity, responsiveness to their needs, the desire to withdraw from participating in the research activity by respecting international humanitarian law and by ensuring that the participant’s rights are protected throughout the conduct of the research.
- **Informed consent:** A written consent will be obtained from the participants who were minors. They are asked to write consent together with his/her legal guardian of legal age. In the process, the researcher shall ensure. Those participants have information and understanding of the purpose of the research, its expected duration, and procedures. Similarly, they were informed of their right to decline to participants and to withdraw from the research. Once the research activity began the researcher may also provide an opportunity for the prospective participants to ask questions and receive answers.
- **Confidentiality and privacy:** The researcher had a primary obligation and took reasonable precautions to protect confidential information obtained through or stored in any medium, in the conduct of this research; the

researcher has not disclosed the identities of the subject at any time. Only the main proponent of the study is considered as the actual contact information of the subjects. The data obtained during the study under the researcher, guidance. And counseling department, and have kept in confidentiality until deemed necessary to do so. The raw data available in both hard and soft copy, and have been accessed only by the researcher and mentor for data analysis.

- **Debriefing:** The researchers would ensure that after data collection, participants are informed about the full aims of the research. Ideally, they should also have access to any publication arising from the study they took part in.
- **Right to Withdraw:** The researcher ensures that participants can feel free to withdraw from participation in the study without fear of penalized.
- **Plagiarism:** The researchers have presented another researcher's work as her own, even if the other work or data source is cited occasionally.
- **Storage of Data:** The raw data and analysis from this study have been stored for up to five years in a safe place that can be accessed only by the researcher and guidance department.

As a guide the interpretation of the coefficient-specific ranges of r corresponding to various interpretations.

Absolute value of r	Interpretation (degree of correlation)
0.9 to 1.0	Very high
0.7 to 0.9	High
0.4 to 0.7	Moderate
0.2 to 0.4	Small
Less than 0.2	Negligible

XI. RESULT

Table 1: Level of Stress among Indians due to covid-19 pandemic

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
Stress	2.40	.395	Strongly Agree	Very high level of stress/very low level of emotional reactions.

Table 1 shows the mean, standard deviation, description, and verbal interpretation of the level of stress due to the covid-19 pandemic among corresponding respondents. It can be seen from the table that the respondents have a high level of stress (mean=2.40, standard deviation =0.395).

Table 2: Emotional reactions among Indians due to covid-19 pandemic

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
Emotional reactions	2.55	0.481	Agree	High level of stress/ low level of emotional reactions.

Table 2 shows the mean, standard deviation, description, and verbal interpretation of emotional reactions among Indians. It can be seen from the table that the respondents have a high level of stress/ low level of emotional reactions (mean= 2.55, standard deviation of Indian psychology students = 0.481)

Of the 80 respondents, 60% indicated the increase of stress and anxiety due to the Covid-19 outbreak. Multiple stressors were identified that contributed to the increased level of stress and its effect on emotions. These included fear and worry about their mental health and of their loved ones (60/80, 60% reported negative impacts of the pandemic), difficulty in concentrating, disruptions to sleeping patterns,

decreased social interactions due to physical distancing, and decreased concerns on academic performance. To cope with stress, anxiety, participants have sought to sort concerns from others and seek help from others and help themselves by adopting a positive attitude coping mechanism.

XII. CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

In this study, we examined emotional responses to the potential threat of the Covid19 pandemic. Since most people in this situation have changed their specific behaviors and habits, the second objective was to examine the contribution of basic personality traits and new habits, developed during the pandemic, to emotional reactions. Among the effects of the pandemic identified, the most prominent was worries about one's mental health and the health of loved ones. These findings are in line with recent studies in china that also found concerns relating to the health of oneself and a family member being highly prevalent among the general population during the pandemic.

The most important result of this study is that worry and fear caused a disturbance in the mental health of some populations. Worry usually arises in the potential. The findings indicate that about 45% of the respondents had negative emotional reactions and 6% believed they were not experiencing any sort of emotional reaction because of this pandemic. Emotional reactions were higher among younger participants. The qualitative study expanded our understanding of the psychological changes people underwent. Participants described their sense of shock and chaos at the outbreak of the epidemic and followed by a gradual process of adjustment to the new situation along with fears and concerns for their welfare and that of their loved ones. The emergence of mental health issues in the wake of life-threatening events has been demonstrated among survivors of coronavirus infection outbreaks, who exhibited stress, worry due to the pandemic. Examinations of the mental health status of the general population during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed signs of stress, anxiety, and depression in India. Since COVID19 is a global threat, all the news and media channels provide continuous coverage of the pandemic.

The qualitative study revealed people's prevailing sense of confusion and chaos at the time of the outbreak, students need to readjust to their new situations and their concern for their families. Moreover, most people locked down in their houses watch News non-stop and tend to panic about the rising numbers of infections and death. Indeed, media exposure is another possible explanation for the high levels of stress and emotional response emerging in this study. Students are facing loss in their studies. These all things lead to cause disturbance in their mental health. Although the covid19 pandemic seems to have resulted in widespread forced adoption of the health services to deliver psychiatric and mental health support, more research is needed to investigate use beyond Covid19 as well as to improve preparedness for rapid virtualization of psychiatric counseling or tele psychiatry. The study concludes that students are having a high level of stress and by increasing days stress is also getting increased. Academic,

environmental, social and health problems all play a specific role in the development of stress. Teaching techniques and the college environment should be adapted to the needs of students. The production utilization of existing student welfare systems, development of a more "student-friendly" environment, and regular periodic extracurricular activities with universal participation can prove to be useful stress-busters. Due to the long-lasting pandemic situation and onerous measures such as lockdown and stay in home orders, the Covid-19 pandemic brings negative impacts on higher education. The findings of our study highlight the urgent need to develop interventions and preventive strategies to address the mental health of students.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Pilcher JJ, Michalowski KR, Carrigan Rd (2001). The prevalence of stress and its relationship to emotional reactions. *Behav Med.* 27:71–6. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- [2.] Wang C, Pan R, Wan X, et al. Immediate psychological responses and associated factors during the initial stage of the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) epidemic among the general population in china. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(5):1729.
- [3.] Indian Ministry of Health. The novel coronavirus. 2020. <https://govextra.gov.il/ministry-of-health/corona/corona-virus-en/> [assessed October 6, 2020].
- [4.] Indian Ministry of Health. The novel coronavirus. 2020. <https://govextra.gov.il/ministry-of-health/corona/corona-virus-en/> [assessed April 24, 2020].
- [5.] Sheikh, Knvul; Rabin, Roni Caryn (10 March 2020). "The Coronavirus: What Scientists Have Learned So Far". *The New York Times*. Retrieved 24 March 2020.
- [6.] "India most infected by Covid-19 among Asian countries and showing its impact by implementing stress and emotional reactions, leaves Turkey behind". *Hindustan Times*. 29 May 2020. Retrieved 30 May 2020.
- [7.] Stein-Zamir C, Abramson N, Shoob H, et al. A large COVID-19 outbreak in a high school 10 days after schools' reopening, Israel, May 2020. *Eurosurveillance.* 2020;25(29):2001352.
- [8.] Jiang F, Deng L, Zhang L, et al. Review of the clinical characteristics of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Gen Int Med.* 2020;35:1545–9.
- [9.] Bhattacharya, Amit (24 May 2021). "India's Covid toll tops 3 lakh, 50,000 deaths in 12 days". *The Times of India*. Retrieved 24 May 2021.
- [10.] Creswell JW, Poth CN. *Qualitative Inquiry Research Methods: Choosing Among Five Approaches*, 4th ed. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi: Sage; 2018. [Google Scholar]
- [11.] Brinkman S, Kvale S. *Interviews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*, 3rd ed. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi: Sage; 2015. [Google Scholar]

- [12.] Prasad, R (15 January 2020). "Vaccine dilemma — to take or not to take Covaxin". The Hindu. Chennai.
- [13.] Bindu Shajan Perappadan (16 January 2020). "Covaxin recipients asked to sign consent form on 'clinical trial mode'". The Hindu. New Delhi. Retrieved 5 June 2021.
- [14.] Krishnan, Murali (26 April 2021). "Coronavirus: Is India counting all COVID deaths?". DW. Retrieved 23 May 2021.
- [15.] Chatterjee, Patralekha (5 September 2020). "Is India missing COVID-19 deaths?". The Lancet. 396 (10252): 657. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31857-2. ISSN 0140-6736. PMC 7470692. PMID 32891197.
- [16.] Bhardwaj, Deeksha (10 April 2020). "Covid-19 crisis: States asked to fill 227 vacancies for epidemiologists". Hindustan Times. Retrieved 23 May 2021.
- [17.] Varshney, Vibha (24 July 2021). "India's mysterious diseases: What is NCDC doing?". Down to Earth. Retrieved 23 May 2021.
- [18.] Krishnan, Vidya (22 April 2021). "India's COVID-19 taskforce did not meet in February, March despite surge, say members". The Caravan. Retrieved 20 May 2021. Another significant lapse, the members told me, the Indian Council of Medical Research's failure to update the treatment protocol for COVID-19 in the past nine months, since July 2020.
- [19.] Rampal, Nikhil (12 May 2021). "Why India's second wave has been deadlier, explained in five charts". mint. Retrieved 23 May 2021.
- [20.] Menon, Gautam I. (24 October 2020). "Problems with the Indian supermodel for COVID-19". The Hindu. ISSN 0971-751X. Retrieved 20 May 2021.
- [21.] IANS (4 May 2021). "Couldn't predict exact nature of second Covid wave: Supermodel Committee". Business Standard India. Retrieved 20 May 2021.
- [22.] Banaji, Murad (14 May 2021). "Flawed science propped up India's second COVID-19 wave". The Caravan. Retrieved 20 May 2021.
- [23.] M, Kaunain Sheriff (5 May 2021). "Third Covid wave inevitable, didn't foresee current ferocity: Scientific Advisor to PM". The Indian Express. Retrieved 23 May 2021.
- [24.] Wallen, Joe (28 March 2020). "40,000 Indians quarantined after 'super spreader' ignores government advice". The Telegraph. Retrieved 30 May 2021.
- [25.] Jump up to: a b "Coronavirus: India 'super spreader' quarantines 40,000 people". BBC News. 27 March 2020. Retrieved 30 May 2021.
- [26.] "Septuagenarian Sikh priest infected 27 of total 38 coronavirus cases in Punjab". India Today. PTI. 28 March 2020. Retrieved 30 May 2021.
- [27.] "India's Covid-19 shortages spur black market for drugs, oxygen". France 24. AFP. 22 April 2021. Retrieved 11 May 2021.
- [28.] "U.S. drugmakers step up supplies as India battles COVID-19 surge". Reuters. 26 April 2021. Retrieved 11 May 2021.
- [29.] Sharma, Manoj (12 November 2020). "Govt announces Atmanirbhar Bharat 3.0; claims COVID stimulus now worth Rs 29.8 lakh crore". Business Today. Retrieved 26 November 2020.
- [30.] Ram, Anya Bharat (1 May 2020). "Monthly Policy Review: April 2020. Rs 15,000 crore sanctioned towards the COVID-19 Emergency Response and Health System Preparedness Package". PRS Legislative Research. Retrieved 21 May 2021.